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Mechatronics and cyber-physical systems

Additiv hergestellte Lösungen für die Kiefer- und Gesichtschirurgie

(Translation in consultation with first examiner)

Additively Manufactured Solutions for Maxillofacial Surgeries

Master thesis to obtain the academic degree:

Master of Engineering (M.Eng.)

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DECLARATION

Declaration

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(Additiv hergestellte Lösungen für die Kiefer- und Gesichtschirurgie)

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Abstract

Every generation has its own pace with technology. Additive Manufacturing, which is also being considered as a part of Fourth industrial revolution, with its unique design, high complexity, and precise manufacturing methods, has become a widely used manufacturing technology in medical applications. With the continuous enrichment of imaging methods in imaging technology, and the continuous improvement of the time and spatial resolution of data collection, we have gradually entered a new era of digital medicine. The combination of 3D printing technology and medical imaging technology has opened a new field for the development of modern clinical medical tools and has also promoted 3D printing into a new development direction. With the continuous development of new materials and technologies, the connection between imaging data and 3D printing technology is getting closer and closer. Collecting image data and performing three-dimensional digital modeling is the basis for realizing medical 3D printing. In recent years, use of Additive manufacturing construct various shapes of prosthesis with improved accuracy, matching the maxillofacial defect precisely. It is considered one of the best methods to manufacture prosthesis for maxillofacial defects.

The purpose of this thesis is to study the integrated digital design techniques for prosthetics of maxillofacial defects, and to research about the prototype production, to create a reference guide for fabricating fixed dental prostheses in clinical practice. The goal of this thesis is to present a method for mandibular reconstruction using additively manufactured components personalized to the patient, injury, and surgeon's operating technique with the help of existing used cases at Gramm GmbH, Regensburg, and the existing literature. At the end of this study, I have presented a detailed guide, which enables the reader to provide additively manufactured solutions for maxillofacial surgeries. This thesis can be used by the professionals in both medical and engineering fields and it contains both: the medical explanations and engineering approach.

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Introduction

Motivation:

Engineers always thrive for the better quality of human lives. World has seen so many inventions by the engineers from the iron age – 1000 BC to the current Fourth industrial revolution. On the other hand, we have doctors who directly impact human lives by treating them. The latest trends in technologies have combined the efforts of doctors and engineers and the results have been miracles. The streams like Biomedical engineering and clinical engineering have been emerged. As an engineer, it always fascinated me to know the application of engineering on medical field. The motivation for this research was initiated with a conversation with my colleague about a dentist appointment and my research in prosthodontics.

Figure 1:Reconstructed mandible ready for printing

I started researching about prosthodontics as each one of us visits a dentist quite often. My research has made me realize that the maxillofacial surgeries are one of the most common surgeries and the quality of the surgery can be increased to a great extent by using additive manufacturing. Generally, the surgeons use CT scans for studying patients' condition and perform the surgery. The Output of a CT scan data is a digital model, which is the input for

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additive manufacturing. Additive manufacturing, by its definition is ‘Converting a digital model into a physical model, in a layer-by-layer approach’.

After the research I have come up with an idea to create a guide for using additive manufacturing for maxillofacial surgeries. The idea is to work on a real time medical case and to create a solution and then document all the steps required to provide a solution for the cases with maxillofacial defects. The document has been presented with the sequence of operations for achieving the results. This document can guide an engineer or a surgeon to create customized solution for patient specific needs. The data from CT scan has been used for this thesis. Softwares InVesalius, Blender, Netfabb and Prusa has been used to create, edit and designing the 3D files. The purpose of this research is to provide a guide to develop surgical solutions i.e., guides or implants for patients with a less price and a less lead time which is 7 days. The research is in collaboration with Gramm GmbH, located in Regensburg, Bayern, and all the resources are according to privacy protection of the acquired data from the respective contacts.

This document consists of medical background and the explanations of different cases of maxillofacial surgeries as the design engineer should be aware of the medical terms, requirements, and surgical procedures in order to provide a customized solutions for patient specific needs.

Figure 2 : Implant ready for printing

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State of Art:

In medical field, prosthodontics is the one of the earliest departments which has started using 3d printing. Prosthodontics [1], also known as dental prosthetics or prosthetic dentistry, is the area of dentistry that focuses on dental prostheses. 3D printing is widely being used for creating the models for surgical assistance and being used for creating the implants. For the understanding the workflow better to show the existing applications of additive manufacturing, this chapter lists down the existing solutions in the field of prosthodontics.

Xilloc Patient specific implants [2]:

This is a company located in Netherlands, who has successfully replaced the whole lower jaw for an 83-year-old patient in 2011. This was featured as ‘The world’s first 3D printed jaw construction’

Figure 3 : Xilloc’s 3D printed lower mandible

Media Lab: IMPLANT 3D [3]

Media lab is company located in Italy, which does not directly provide implants but provides software solutions and enables the user to design the surgical guides. The software is named as ‘Implant 3D’. The software must be bought by the user i.e., the surgeon or the engineer. This software is labelled as ‘Guide design software’ by the company. This software was launched in 2017 whilst the first version of Implant 3D software for implant planning and guided surgery was released in 2007.

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Materialise:

Materialise [4] is a public Company located in Leuven, Belgium. Materialize also provides medical solutions for the surgeons with the name ‘Materialise Personalized Solutions’. They provide the solutions for Orthognathic, neuro and reconstructive surgeries and design and produce splints, guides, and implants.

Gramm GmbH:

Gramm [5] is the company which is located in Regensburg, Germany. Gramm has been providing patient specific implants in the field of the prosthodontics. The solutions include providing the 3D models for the guided surgeries. Gramm also provides solutions for cranial surgeries.

Figure 4 : Cranial implant designed by Gramm GmbH

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Background Study:

Before getting into design or technical details, this chapter discusses the details about the need of a maxillofacial surgery. As an engineer, one might not be aware of the conditions required for the surgery. This chapter provides a brief introduction to the medical details, different scenarios of maxillofacial surgeries, the technologies used for capturing the patient's data, and discusses about the history of additive manufacturing in medical field and prosthodontics.

Mandibular reconstruction one of the most common surgeries in prosthodontics and is required for stage 3 and above oral cavity cancer. Oral cavity cancer is a disease in which malignant (cancer) cells form in the lips or mouth and it is a type of head and neck cancer.

The oral cavity includes the following [6]:

- The front two thirds of the tongue [7].
- The gingiva (gums).
- The buccal mucosa (the lining of the inside of the cheeks).
- The floor (bottom) of the mouth under the tongue.
- The hard palate (the roof of the mouth).
- The retromolar trigone (the small area behind the wisdom teeth).

Figure 5:Representation of Oral cavity

Anatomy of the oral cavity: The oral cavity includes the lips, hard palate (the bony front portion of the roof of the mouth), soft palate (the muscular back portion of the roof of the mouth), retromolar trigone (the area behind the wisdom teeth), front two-thirds of the tongue, gingiva (gums), buccal mucosa (the inner lining of the lips and cheeks), and floor of the mouth under the tongue.

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Oral Cavity cancer can be diagnosed using the following methods:

1. Physical exam of the lips and oral cavity
2. Endoscopy
3. Biopsy
4. Exfoliative cytology
5. MRI (magnetic resonance imaging)
6. CT scan
7. Barium Swallow
8. PET scan (positron emission tomography scan)
9. Bone Scan
 - CT scans will be discussed further as these scans provide 3d Data, which can be used further for providing additively manufactured solutions.

Stages of Lip and Oral Cavity Cancer:

After lip and oral cavity cancer has been diagnosed, tests are done to find out if cancer cells have spread within the lip and oral cavity or to other parts of the body. There are three ways that cancer spreads in the body.

The following stages are used for lip and oral cavity cancer [8]:

- Stage 0 (Carcinoma in Situ)
- Stage I
- Stage II
- Stage III
- Stage IV

Stage III or above of oral cavity cancer can lead to damage of the jaws as the increased size of tumor damages the muscle tissue along with the bone surrounding the same. There are two types of standard treatments which are being used for treating the tumor:

1. Surgery
2. Radiation Therapy

This research paper particularly focuses on ‘surgical procedures’ as treatment and no other oral cavity cancer treatments are discussed.

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Surgery:

Surgery [9] is the removal of the tumor and some surrounding healthy tissue [10], known as a margin, during the operation. The most common surgical procedures for the removal of the tumor are: Primary tumor surgery, Glossectomy, Mandibulectomy, Maxillectomy. If treatment requires removing large areas of tissue, reconstructive surgery may be necessary to help the patient. As a part of the reconstructive surgery, Healthy bone or tissue may be taken from other parts of the body to fill gaps left by the tumor or replace part of the lip, tongue, palate, or jaw.

History of Utilization of Three-dimensional Imaging Technology to Enhance Maxillofacial Surgical Applications:

The advent of computed tomography (CT) [11] in dentistry began in the late 1980s with the use of medical-grade machines located in major hospitals or radiology centers. Patients were referred for CT scans to achieve a level of diagnosis beyond the scope of conventional two-dimensional panoramic or periodical radiography available in most dental offices. As computing power increased, the ability to move from two-dimensional to three-dimensional data marked the beginning of a new and exciting area in diagnostic imaging, paving the way for the development and adoption of interactive treatment planning software to help interpret the massive amount of anatomic data.

The information gained from a CT scan allowed the clinician to appreciate the “reality of anatomy” for each patient presentation—yielding views of structures aided by advances in data processing power of the computer-driven technology. CT technology and interactive treatment planning software applications helped bridge the communication gap between all members of the implant team, while appreciably removing the guesswork from the process. Recently, a new family of imaging machines was introduced with cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) technology, which offered several immediate benefits for dental applications by helping to remove many of the barriers associated with the imaging modality.

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CT scan:

A computerized tomography scan [11] (CT or CAT scan) uses computers and rotating X-ray machines to create cross-sectional images of the body. These images provide more detailed information than normal X-ray images. They can show the soft tissues, blood vessels, and bones in various parts of the body.

Figure 6: GE LightSpeed CT scanner at Open House, Monroeville, Pennsylvania

CBCT scan:

Cone-beam computed tomography systems (CBCT) [12] are a variation of traditional computed tomography (CT) systems. The CBCT systems used by dental professionals rotate around the patient, capturing data using a cone-shaped X-ray beam.

These data are used to reconstruct a three-dimensional (3D) image of the following regions of the patient's anatomy: dental (teeth); oral and maxillofacial region (mouth, jaw, and neck); and ears, nose, and throat ("ENT").

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Figure 7 : Cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) data display four primary views: the axial view (A), the panoramic view (B), the three-dimensional reconstructed view (C), and the cross-sectional views (D)

Additive Manufacturing in Medical Field:

3D printing, also known as additive manufacturing (AM), is a technology that uses three-dimensional (model data as the basis and uses bondable materials such as powdered metal or plastic to manufacture products with multi-level structures or complex geometric shapes.

As a new type of molding technology with rapid development and great potential, 3D printing technology has a wide range of applications in fields of medicine, aerospace, automobile, and food. For example, 3D printed knee meniscus and heart valves, satellites are equipped with multiple 3D printed aluminum alloy components, 3D printed candies, chocolates, sushi, etc.

In addition, in the field of cultural heritage protection and restoration, there are also 3D printing technologies. For example, researchers from the Maidstone Museum [13] in the United Kingdom used 3D printing technology to reshape the face of a mummy which is 2500 years old.

Although 3D printing technology has a wide range of applications, it is currently widely used in the field of biomedicine. In 1993, the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) [14] obtained a patent for 3D printing technology based on the principle of inkjet printing. Since

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then, MIT has been at the forefront of biological printing technology. The research team was led by Professor Robert Langer.

3D printing technology principle and classification:

In 1986, Charles Hull developed 3D printing technology based on the stereolithography process. The main principle of 3D printing technology is "manufacturing: layer by layer from a digital model", the printing process mainly divided into five parts:

1. Design: using computer-aided design software (SolidWorks, AutoCAD) to design digital 3D printing objects
2. Save: save the designed 3D printing object in a format readable by a 3D printer. Common file formats include stereolithography (STL) files and virtual reality modeling language (VRML)
3. File transfer: The file is exported into the printer (G-code)
4. Printing: according to the characteristics of the raw materials and product requirements the appropriate filaments/Materials are selected, and the printing temperature, speed, pressure, and other related parameters are set
5. Post-processing, where the surface of the product is processed after printing

One of the most spoken advantage is a 3D printer can complete the entire manufacturing process as a standalone unit, and process is more simplified. 3D printing technology is suitable to produce small batches of production with complex structures. Traditional manufacturing methods focus on the production of large-scale parts require mass production. Therefore, 3D printing technology and traditional manufacturing technology complement each other and jointly promote modern manufacturing to smart Transformation of globalized digitization and networked manufacturing. At present, in the medical field, there are many types of 3D printing technologies used, mainly including the following: light curing (stereo lithography apparatus, SLA), multi-jet (multi jet, MJ), polymer jet (poly-jet, PJ), digital light processing (DLP), selective laser sintering (SLS), direct metal laser sintering (DMLS), color-jet (CJ), melting Deposition (fused deposition modeling, FDM), laminated object manufacturing (LOM), electron beam melting (EBM) etc.

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Application of 3D printing technology in the medical field [15]:

Medical models:

With the rapid development of CT (computer tomography), MRI (magnetic resonance imaging), PET (position emission computed tomography) and other technologies and digital medical technology, medical personnel can easily and accurately obtain three-dimensional data information of biological bodies. With the help of 3D printing technology, three-dimensional medical models will be quickly constructed.

The medical model constructed can be used in medical teaching and surgical simulation and has great practical significance. For example, doctors can diagnose the patient's condition based on the medical model, formulate relevant surgical plans, study surgical procedures, and simulate surgery.

The application of medical models will make the operation more precise, shorten the operation time, improve the success rate of complicated and difficult operations, and reduce the probability of related complications.

Figure 8 : Models printed on Mimaki 3DUJ-553 printer [16]

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Permanent implants:

3D printing technology also has broad application prospects in terms of permanent implants. Taking bone implants as an example, the shape of human bones is unique and distinctive. Traditional artificial bone implants cannot achieve the ideal 100% match with the biological body and are accompanied by long manufacturing cycles and high costs. Disadvantages. The emergence of 3D printing technology makes it possible to achieve 100% matching of implants. 3D printing technology can customize the shape of bone implants according to the characteristics of the patient's own bones, and 3D printing technology can accurately control the porosity and the size of the pores of the bone implants according to the internal structural characteristics of the individual's own bones. Construct an implant whose shape and structure match the biological body. The cost of highly matched implants constructed by 3D printing technology is relatively low. It will alleviate the pain of patients and reduce the economic burden of patients. Therefore, it will inevitably promote the development of medical implants.

Scaffolds – Tissue engineering [17]:

Compared with traditional tissue engineering scaffold preparation technology, the main advantages of 3D printing technology are: the prepared porous scaffold can have 100% connectivity, and the shape and structure of the scaffold are no longer restricted by traditional processes; at the same time, the 3D printing technology adopts CAD/ The CAM software system precisely controls the porosity and pore structure of the internal communicating pores of the tissue engineering scaffold, and constructs the most reasonable microenvironment for the normal growth, reproduction and migration of cells, as well as the delivery of oxygen and nutrients. In addition, due to the precise control of computer-aided equipment, the process of preparing tissue engineering scaffolds by 3D printing technology has good repeatability.

Figure 9 : 3D Printed spinal implant [18]

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3D printing process and its application in the field of prosthodontics:

In medical field, prosthodontics is the one of the earliest departments which has started using 3d printing. Prosthodontics [19], also known as dental prosthetics or prosthetic dentistry, is the area of dentistry that focuses on dental prostheses. 3D printing is widely being used for creating the models for surgical assistance and also being used for creating the implants. Application of additive manufacturing can be explained in 3 steps:

1. Data acquisition
2. Data Processing
3. 3D Printing

1. Data acquisition:

The choice of three-dimensional data acquisition method is an important step in determining the accuracy of the digital model. Digital optical impression collection technology has been recognized as the development trend of dental prosthetics impression collection technology, including the method of extraoral collection, that is, the use of digital scanning equipment to scan the patient's dentition model to obtain digital impressions and intraoral collection methods.

2. Data processing:

After data acquisition, use the software to trim the data for three-dimensional reconstruction. First use the segmentation tool to simply segment the target area. The segmented target area is gridded. The image is composed of a certain number of triangles. The number of triangles determines the precision of the digital model. The more the number, the greater the amount of data, the smoother the surface of the model. Then use visualization tools for surface rendering, maximum or minimum intensity projection and multi-plane reconstruction. The data forms the STL file, and the CAD software edits the file to form the digital crown/bridge and other restoration models.

3. 3D printing:

3D printing as the final step, the three-dimensional model printed is a continuous ultra-thin layer accumulated layer by layer with the desired layer thickness. Its application in the field of stomatology includes three technologies: Selective Laser Sintering (SLS), Stereolithography (SLA), Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM).

The principle of SLS is to use a high-intensity laser beam to focus on the powder bed to melt the powder into a solid thin layer. After the sintering of one layer is completed, the powder bed drops, and the next layer is sintered and merged with the

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previous layer. When all layers are sintered After the completion of the parts production is completed. When the selected material is metal powder to complete the restoration, the laser irradiates the unit area to produce energy sintered powder. Due to the improper selection of the molding parameters during the sintering process, the spheroidization phenomenon occurs when the surface layer of the part is superimposed on the layer during the sintering process, that is, molten/sintered metal. Under the action of the interfacial tension of the surrounding medium, there is a phenomenon of transformation of the sintered molecules into a spherical surface and thus causing the adhesion between the molecules to form consistent layers. Studies have shown that SLS and by conventional casting technology to produce metal crown portion of the cobalt-chromium alloy having similar binding strength, and because of the phenomenon of the ball With the existence of SLS, the metal inner crown made by SLS has a larger surface area and is easier to combine with the porcelain layer, and the required load for fracture of the metal inner crown made by SLS is 1087.2M Pa greater than the maximum occlusal load of the posterior teeth 1031M Pa. The powder materials selected by SLS are thermoplastic materials, including resin materials, casting waxes, metal materials, ceramic materials, and thermoplastic composites. Therefore, in contrast, it has great advantages in the application of dental medicine. SLS is suitable for making metal and alloy base crowns, bridges, titanium alloy implants.

SLA uses liquid photosensitive resin as the raw material. The principle is to separate the CAD geometric model through layered discrete software and input it into the CNC molding system. The ultraviolet laser beam, controlled by the program irradiates the liquid resin on the model building platform to scan the area. The resin is cured point by point, and then the platform is lowered to a height, and a new layer of liquid resin is covered on the formed layer, and the newly cured layer is firmly combined with the previous layer, and finally a resin model is formed. The advantages of SLA are high molding accuracy and good detail reproduction, but the disadvantage is that the daily maintenance of light curing equipment is difficult, the cost of materials used is high, and it does not conform to economic principles. SLA is suitable to produce implant surgical guides, fixed repair, and movable repair resin investment molds.

The principle of FDM is to preheat the thermoplastic material to a certain temperature to make it into a semi-liquid state. In this state, it is ejected from the nozzle. The movement trajectory of the nozzle is set by the computer program, and the ejected liquid layer and the operating platform The upper layer is solidified and combined

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within 0.1sec, and a solid body is formed through the superposition of layers. FDM is suitable for thermoplastic materials, which can be used to make resin investment molds, embed wax molds for casting, and implant surgical guides. The advantages of FDM are simple equipment maintenance, low cost, and fast speed. The disadvantages are low accuracy and complex components need support

Theoretical Foundation of Mandibular Reconstruction:

Mandibular reconstruction has changed significantly over the years and continues to evolve with the introduction of newer technologies and techniques. A significant number of the research papers on Mandibular reconstruction Additive manufacturing studied. In this chapter, the theoretical foundation of few of the earlier research is discussed. This chapters includes the proposed models and hypothesis of the existing research. This chapter also includes the case study a successful mandibular reconstruction surgery using additive manufacturing.

History of Mandibular reconstruction [20]:

Taylor and Watson presented the first free groin-iliac crest osteocutaneous flap based on superficial circumflex iliac artery in 1978. In 1979, he improved the free transfer of iliac crest osteocutaneous flap by involving the deep circumflex iliac artery. In 1994, Koshima et al. further modified the iliac crest osteocutaneous flap by using the lateral circumflex femoral artery to repair large mandibular defects. Long before attempting the reconstruction surgery, a research paper with the title ‘The Use of Autogenous Cartilage Graft in Arthroplasty for True Ankylosis of Temporo-mandibular Joint’ in 1951.

Reconstructive Strategies:

In order to achieve a normal contour for the mandible, multiple osteotomies are often required. Subsequently, the surgical strategies for reconstructing the mandibular bony defects often vary according to the location and the size of the defects. For ease of differentiation, we modify the classification of mandible defects into central defects (C), true lateral defects (L), and posterior defects (P). The approach to reconstructing the mandibular bony defects is based on the modified CLP classification.

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Figure 10 : Classification of oromandibular defect and recommended surgical strategies in different regions of oromandibular defect

History of Mandibular reconstruction using additive manufacturing [21]:

Computer assisted surgical planning was the beginning of the application of imaging analysis of the data on the three-dimensional orientation of the bone segments during the preoperative planning. Heather et al. applied Virtual surgical planning and Surgical design and simulation to real five cases study with results of obvious benefits in 2013.

Case studies

Case study 1:

Ming-June Tsai and Ching-Tsai Wu from Cheng Kung University [22], created the processes of one-stop solution of mandible construction which the surgical processes for patients with oral cancer were simulated, including completion of mandible lesion resection, preparing fibula pieces, recombining the fibula and completion of the mandible defect reconstruction.

Methods: The mentioned research included a 5-step approach for a successful mandibular reconstruction as mentioned below:

1. Model digitizing and parameterization
2. pre-surgical planning and design,
3. cutting fixture design
4. cutting fixture rapid manufacturing
5. assembly and verification.

The six steps to fulfill the mandibular reconstruction postulated by this study are as follows:

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1. Input the patient's 3D mandible model into the CAMRP. The doctor then decides the cutting nodes to remove the lesion portion.
2. The CAMRP performs surgical planning and generates 3D models of the cutting jigs and fixture.
3. Output the physical cutting jigs and fixture by 3D printing technology.
4. Use the guiding jigs to cut the portion of the mandible.
5. Harvest the fibula, place it on the fixture, and cut into pieces based on the lengths computed by the CAMRP.
6. Assemble the fibular segments into a registering fixture for mandibular reconstruction.

Case study 2 [23]:

Background: Computer-assisted mandibular reconstruction facilitates preoperative surgery simulation and transfers the virtual plan to a real operation.

This systematic review and meta-analysis aimed to compare the accuracy, efficiency, postoperative complications, and economic viability between computer assisted mandibular reconstruction and conventional freehand mandibular reconstruction.

Methods: The PubMed, Embase, Cochrane Library, and Google Scholar data bases were searched up to November of 2018 [24]. The accuracy, efficiency, postoperative complications, and economic viability of computer-assisted mandibular reconstruction compared to conventional freehand mandibular reconstruction were systematically reviewed. Continuous and dichotomous data were pooled in mean difference (or standardized mean difference if necessary) and odds ratio, subsequently, with 95 percent confidence interval.

Results:

A total of 12 studies were included in the systematic review, and data extracted from 11 of them were combined in meta-analysis. The accuracy of computer-assisted mandibular reconstruction was better than or equal to that of conventional freehand mandibular reconstruction according to qualitative analysis, although the quantitative comparison from meta-analysis was excluded because of the diversity of measurements. As for efficiency, computer-assisted mandibular reconstruction, when compared to conventional freehand mandibular reconstruction, revealed a shorter ischemic time, reconstructive time, total operative time, and length of stay. There was no difference in postoperative complication rate.

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Conclusions:

Computer-assisted mandibular reconstruction showed increased efficiency considering the reduced ischemic time, total operative time, reconstructive time, and length of stay. However, the accuracy, reconstruction outcomes, and perioperative cost should be further elucidated because of diverse measurements and the lack of included studies.

Thesis Structure:

1. Acquiring the clinical data through the company contacts (patient's information is secured and the information is not shared according to the data protection)
2. Creating raw STL file from DICOM data using InVesalius.
3. STL editing on blender
4. Preparing the 3d Model.
5. Slicing (G-code generation on Prusa)
6. Prototype production
7. Quality check
8. Iteration of step 4 to step 7 till the satisfactory results are achieved.

Model Generation

Case Details for Thesis:

The used case for this thesis is a patient (details are not disclosed), who has an oral cavity cancer which has led to the damage in the left side of the mandible. The patient already had an implant which unfortunately was not comfortable for the patient and causing an extreme pain. Thus, the surgeon has decided to create a new implant and replace the old implant. The aim is to create and construct the 3D model of the mandible and design a new implant and provide the digital file to the surgeon.

STL file Generation – InVesalius

For Additive manufacturing or 3D printing, the initial requirement is a CAD file or a 3D design file. This 3d file is often designed using the design softwares. Another way of obtaining this file is through reverse engineering. Reverse engineering enables the user to replicate the object. There are different types of 3d Scanners with the purpose of reverse engineering. There are multiple approaches for reverse engineering. The files which have been used in this thesis are DICOM files. Medical industry has been using 3D scans for the better understanding of patient's condition and Additive manufacturing enabled the freedom of printing those digital data.

DICOM - Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine [25] is the standard for the communication and management of medical imaging information and related data. DICOM is most commonly used for storing and transmitting medical images enabling the integration of medical imaging devices such as scanners, servers, workstations, printers, network hardware, and picture archiving and communication systems (PACS) from multiple manufacturers. It has been widely adopted by hospitals and is making inroads into smaller applications such as dentists' and doctors' offices.

DICOM files can be exchanged between two entities that can receive image and patient data in DICOM format. The data will be given by the hospital after the CT scan which consists of a vast number of files. The used case had 509 files.

Name	Status	Date modified	Type	Size
000	⊙ R	7/3/2019 7:28 PM	File	670 KB
001	⊙ R	7/3/2019 7:28 PM	File	514 KB
002	⊙ R	7/3/2019 7:30 PM	File	514 KB
003	⊙ R	7/3/2019 7:29 PM	File	514 KB
004	⊙ R	7/3/2019 7:29 PM	File	514 KB
005	⊙ R	7/3/2019 7:30 PM	File	514 KB
006	⊙ R	7/3/2019 7:28 PM	File	514 KB
007	⊙ R	7/3/2019 7:28 PM	File	514 KB
008	⊙ R	7/3/2019 7:28 PM	File	514 KB
009	⊙ R	7/3/2019 7:28 PM	File	514 KB
010	⊙ R	7/3/2019 7:29 PM	File	514 KB
011	⊙ R	7/3/2019 7:29 PM	File	514 KB
012	⊙ R	7/3/2019 7:28 PM	File	514 KB
013	⊙ R	7/3/2019 7:28 PM	File	514 KB
014	⊙ R	7/3/2019 7:28 PM	File	514 KB
015	⊙ R	7/3/2019 7:27 PM	File	514 KB
016	⊙ R	7/3/2019 7:29 PM	File	514 KB
017	⊙ R	7/3/2019 7:29 PM	File	514 KB
018	⊙ R	7/3/2019 7:29 PM	File	514 KB
019	⊙ R	7/3/2019 7:29 PM	File	514 KB
020	⊙ R	7/3/2019 7:29 PM	File	514 KB
021	⊙ R	7/3/2019 7:29 PM	File	514 KB
022	⊙ R	7/3/2019 7:28 PM	File	514 KB

Figure 11 : The list of files in CT scan data

Figure 12 : Properties of a DICOM image

These files cannot be read directly by double clicking the file. One of the ways to open the file is to choose the format 'DICOM', however this will just open the file as an image. This raw data must be processed and must be converted into a digital model. InVesalius - An open-sourced software has been used for this conversion.

InVesalius [26] is a free software for reconstruction of computed tomography and magnetic resonance images. The software is mainly used for rapid prototyping, teaching, forensics, and in the medical field. It is possible to use it on the Microsoft Windows, GNU/Linux and Apple Mac OS X platforms. The software's main features are the ability to import DICOM or Analyze files, to export files to the STL, OBJ, and PLY formats, volume rendering, and manual or semiautomatic image segmentation.

Figure 13 : Interface of InVesalius to download

Conversion of DICOM files:

The STL file generation on InVesalius consists of 4 steps:

1. Load data
2. Creating a Mask
3. Configure 3D surface
4. Export data.

1. Step 1: Load data:

The first step using InVesalius is to load the 'Medical Image data'. The data which is provided from the hospital consists multiple folders. The instructions to choose the right folder for InVesalius is as follows:

1. Go through the all the folders along with subfolders
2. Check the number of images in each folder
3. Select the folder with the maximum number of images.

Figure 14 : Interface of InVesalius

Figure 15 : Importing the DICOM files

Figure 16 : Validating the DICOM files

2. Step 2: Select the region of interest - Create new mask:

Creation of mask is the most important step whilst STL file generation as it determines the properties of the output file. The software comes with predefined set of bone structures. User must select the right bone structure to get the apt 3d Model.

Figure 17 : List of bone structures

As the dataset is a maxillofacial scan of an adult, the adult bone has been selected for the mask generation.

Figure 18 : Mask generation on InVesalius

The values are populated automatically and must not be changed. If there was a mask generated earlier with wrong properties, the option for 'Overwrite last surface' must be selected in order to delete the previously generated surface and create a new one. Once the options are checked and validated, 'Create surface' must be selected for the generation of surface.

3. Step 3: Configuring 3D surface:

Once the surface has been created, the created surface must be configured. In this step, the appearance of the file which will be generated can be adjusted.

Figure 19: Surface generation

For the optimum results surface 2 has been selected with no transparency. This was trial and error with surface 1 and surface 2.

4. Step 4: Export Data:

Once the 3d surface has been generated, the file must be exported from InVesalius. The output file is a .inv3 file which can later be imported in 'Blender' for further editing.

The final steps on InVesalius are:

1. Export the 3D surface as an STL
2. Save the InVesalius file.

One of the most common problems would be the crashing interface of the software. Closing all the other softwares on the working computer and then using InVesalius can resolve this problem.

Figure 20 : Exporting file from InVesalius

Output file:

Figure 21 : Final output file from InVesalius

MODEL MAKING ON BLENDER:

Model Making on Blender:

Separating the Mandible:

After generating the STL on InVesalius, the file should further be imported in Blender for the model generation. The output STL file consists of so many faces and unwanted details which must be cleaned and edited which can be done on Blender.

Blender is a free and open-source 3D computer graphics software toolset used for creating animated films, visual effects, art, 3D printed models, motion graphics, interactive 3D applications, virtual reality, and computer games. Blender's features include 3D modeling, UV unwrapping, texturing, raster graphics editing, rigging, and skinning, fluid and smoke simulation, particle simulation, soft body simulation, sculpting, animating, match moving, rendering, motion graphics, video editing, and compositing.

Figure 22 : Raw output file from InVesalius on Blender

The DICOM files from the CT scan generates the complete skull of the patient, whilst the maxillofacial surgery only needs the model of the lower jaw. This can be done on 'Edit mode' on blender.

MODEL MAKING ON BLENDER:

The generated STL file is always with a large size with a very high number of vertices, edges and faces. This must be edited to process the file easily and to make it a good fit for generative design.

Figure 23 : Cross section of existing implant

Removing the unnecessary part from the STL file:

The Ct scan data provides the file which consists of the complete skull. The first step of process is to separate the mandible from the skull.

Figure 24 : Toolbox in Blender

MODEL MAKING ON BLENDER:

Instructions for editing the file in Blender:

Mode: Edit

Figure 25: Modes in Blender

The default mode on blender is always 'Object' mode which will only allow the user to see the model. The mode must be changed to 'Edit' to modify the file.

Tools which are used on blender for editing are as follows:

1. Select box (cursor left click and hold)
2. Knife (Shift + spacebar +K)
3. Delete Vertices (X)

Process:

1. Use select box for selecting regions which are away from the mandible.
2. User can select the faces or vertices on Blender interface.
3. Once selected, the selection will be highlighted in orange
4. Delete the vertices – Press X for deletion and confirm
5. Once the larger areas are removed, the mandible must be separated from the remaining parts.
6. This can be done using the knife tool.
7. It is suggested for the model to be zoomed in before using the knife tool to avoid cutting the mandible.

MODEL MAKING ON BLENDER:

8. Shift L can be used to select all the linked part, and then can be inverted to remove the parts which are not connected to the mandible.

Figure 26 : The selection box

Figure 27 : Knife tool

MODEL MAKING ON BLENDER:

Editing the Mandible:

Once the mandible has been separated, it is then ready for the reconstruction. The reconstruction of the damaged part is mandatory to design an implant for the same.

The outline of the process is as follows:

1. Clean the file again and double check the design file.
2. Divide the model by selecting the healthy part separating it from the damaged mandible. These two parts can be considered as a damaged part and healthy part.
3. The damaged part must be removed and replaced after reconstructing, taking the healthy part as the reference.
4. The damaged part can be edited and rebuilt in 'Sculpt' mode on blender.
5. Once the damaged part is reconstructed, both the parts must be connected.
6. The whole mandible must be saved as a new 'Reconstructed mandible'

Figure 28 : Raw mandible after editing the STL

MODEL MAKING ON BLENDER:

Workflow on blender to create the mandible:

1. Select the outline of the healthy mandible by selecting the vertices

Figure 29 : Selection of the healthy part of the mandible

2. Separate the selection and save it.

Figure 30 : Cross section of the healthy side of the mandible in object mode

MODEL MAKING ON BLENDER:

3. The healthy part has been named as 'Cube'

Figure 31 : List of files on Blender

4. The part is mirrored and added to the existing model and then edited to fit exactly.

Figure 32 : Editing Cube.001

MODEL MAKING ON BLENDER:

Figure 33 : Mirrored healthy part of the mandible

5. Its mandatory to save all the working files. We can also choose to see or hide different parts on blender.

Figure 34 : List of parts in current design file

6. Align all the parts and check for the gaps between the healthy part of the mandible and the mirrored model as there could either be gaps or overlaps. This step determines whether the parts to be connected or the overlaps has to be removed.

MODEL MAKING ON BLENDER:

Figure 35 : Visible gap between the parts

7. The healthy part in the given case is smaller, thus the parts have to be connected. This can be done by selecting both the parts and the using 'Ctrl+J'. The outer surfaces must be aligned and then selected. However, the output will not be a desired mandible as this part must be filled. Thus, a part of cube.001 has been cut and placed to fill this gap.

MODEL MAKING ON BLENDER:

Figure 36 : Selection of parts

Figure 37 : Cutting the parts to align them symmetrically

MODEL MAKING ON BLENDER:

Figure 38 : Selection of surfaces

8. Once the parts are aligned, a section of Cube 001 is used to attach both the parts.

Figure 39 : Cross section of Cube 001

MODEL MAKING ON BLENDER:

Figure 40: Complete jaw after construction

Figure 41 : Completely reconstructed Mandible

With this step, the reconstruction of mandible is complete. Depending on the particular patient's requirement the next step is to design implants or surgical guides. For this case, the patient needed a new implant. This the next step is to design the implant. Though this case did not require surgical guides, the process of design is explained in later parts.

Implant Design:

Steps for Implant design:

1. Draw the course of the implant along the jaw as a 3D spline (2D sketch, move sketch objects in 3D)
2. Draw the shape of the implant limbs as a solid body (2D sketch, extrude)
3. arrange the links along the course (pattern)
4. Position the limbs individually
5. Connect neighboring links (tangent condition)
6. Round off the ends of the implant
7. Round off the sharp edges of the implant
8. Make the holes depending on the surgeon's requirements (diameter of the screws which will be used in the surgery)

Figure 42 : Drawing in 3D along the mandible

Figure 43 : Extruding the 2D sketch

Figure 44 : Final implant after making the holes

DESIGN OF SURGICAL GUIDES:

Design of Surgical guides:

Steps for the design of surgical guides:

1. Insert a new mesh – box
2. Position it accurately
3. Subdivide the box
4. Fit the ‘faces’ around the mandible exactly
5. Perform ‘Boolean’
6. Save the new part (Cube 002)
7. Export selected part only as STL.

Figure 45: Insertion of Cube

DESIGN OF SURGICAL GUIDES:

Figure 46: Positioning and editing the Cube as a Surgical guide

Figure 47 : Before Boolean operation

DESIGN OF SURGICAL GUIDES:

Figure 48 : Final Surgical Guide

With this step, the designing part is complete. Most of the maxillofacial surgeries require implants or surgical guides.

In case of maxillofacial reconstruction surgeries, the surgical guides are necessary for the replacement bone as well, which can be designed in the same way as the surgical guide for the mandible. The process steps remain the same.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS:

Experimental Results:

Design Output:

1. Mandible:

Figure 49: Mandible

2. Surgical Guide:

Figure 50 : Surgical Guide

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS:

3. Implant:

Figure 51 Implant

Accuracy of the Implant:

The accuracy of the implant has to be checked in order to avoid any kind of errors before the prototype or the end product production. This can be done on Netfabb. The results on Netfabb are as follows:

1. A uniform wall thickness of 3 mm is achieved:

Figure 52 Wall thickness of the implant

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS:

2. The holes are uniform with the radius of 1.150mm as requested by the surgeon.

Figure 53 A: Radius of the implant holes

Figure 54 B: Radius of the implant holes

Once the design process is completed, the models must be checked for errors. The mandible and the surgical guide have been checked for the same and were printed.

PROTOTYPE PRODUCTION:

Prototype Production:

1. Mandible:

AM technology, process, and machine specifications:

AM technology used: VAT Polymerization

Process: Stereolithography

Machine details: Prusa SL1

Resin Used: Prusa: UV sensitive Resin – Tough – Azure blue

Layer Thickness: 0.05 mm

For the prototype production of the mandible, the steps involved are:

1. Slicing the model on Prusa
2. Transferring the data to the printer
3. Printing
4. Post processing
 - a. Support structure removal
 - b. UV curing

1. Slicing the Model on Prusa:

The exported STL file from blender was imported into Prusa and was checked for errors. The model had errors when imported. The errors were as follows:

- a. 6 Backward edges
- b. 42 reversed facets.

As mentioned earlier, the model must be error free in order to be printed. In simple terms, a model which has to be printed using 3D printing must be an airtight model.

PROTOTYPE PRODUCTION:

Figure 55 Errors in the Mandible

This was not checked while printing the prototype in the first time, which has resulted in a failed print.

Figure 56 Failed print

PROTOTYPE PRODUCTION:

Thus, the model was repaired and imported again.

Figure 57 Repaired Mandible Model

Slicing: The layer thickness was selected as the lowest available for the printer which is 0.05 mm for the best surface finish and to avoid the staircase effect completely. The support structures were kept everywhere as for SLA support structures are mandatory.

Figure 58 Model with support structures

PROTOTYPE PRODUCTION:

The model took approximately 7 hours of printing time and was printed without any errors in the second attempt.

Figure 59 Printed model on the build platform

The model was removed from the build plate and the support structures were removed. The part was then kept for UV curing for 15 minutes for the resin to be cured.

Figure 60 Mandible after UV Curing

PROTOTYPE PRODUCTION:

2. Surgical guide:

AM technology, process, and machine specifications:

AM technology used: Material Extrusion

Process: Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM)

Machine details: Prusa i3 Mk3S

Material: PLA

Layer Thickness: 0.05 mm

The surgical guide model did not have any errors. For the support generation for the surgical guide, the brush has been used to select the area where support structured must be enabled.

Figure 61 (A) Support structure selection

PROTOTYPE PRODUCTION:

Once the file has been sliced, it should be exported as G-code, which would then be transferred to the printer.

Figure 62 Surgical Guide - G code

Figure 63 Printed Surgical Guide

Conclusion and Future Works

Conclusion:

Providing a detailed guide for mandibular reconstruction using additively manufactured components personalized to the patient, injury, and surgeon's operating technique was the goal of this thesis. During this research, a method has been developed which have not existed before. This guide enables the surgeon or the engineer to design and provide a solution for maxillofacial surgeries in very short periods. One can provide a solution within a week or two weeks by following the methodology provided in this research.

During the research, there were few challenges while designing and the prototype production. These challenges have been documented as well, which will enable to user to be vigilant and not to make the same mistakes again. A detailed guide for the usage of InVesalius and blender are documented. The user can cross check the modelling phases with the pictures so that any kind of errors don't occur.

The methodology worked accurately, and the goal of thesis has been achieved by the end of the research. The prototypes of the mandible and the surgical guide are aligned perfectly, which shows that this SOP can be used in real time medical cases.

Figure 64: Mandible and the Surgical Guide Alignment

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

The achievements of this thesis are as follows:

1. The intended SOP for additively manufactured has been created.
2. A 3D model of the mandible from CT scan data (DICOM files) was created.
3. Implant and the surgical guide for the patient's mandible were designed.
4. The prototype of the mandible was 3D printed (Stereolithography).
5. Prototype of the surgical guide is 3D printed(FDM).
6. Quality of the prototypes was met.
7. The surgical guide was aligned exactly with the mandible.

Future Works:

The future scope of this work could involve several areas such as:

1. Software selection:

This research has presented a way to use the tools InVesalius, Blender and Netfabb. The research can be extended to find the other usable softwares for providing solutions for maxillofacial surgeries. By doing this, we can enable the user to choose the software of his choice for designing

2. Creating other SOPs:

Through this research, it has been proven that additive manufacturing can provide accurate solutions in medical field i.e., prosthodontics. Thus, this research should be extended to other disciplines of medical field where there is a need prototypes and surgical. The immediate area of research is Cranial implants and Orthopedics.

3. Developing a Script to automate the workflow in each software.

The end goal of any process in this era of IOT is automation. The research should be carried out to write scripts in any programming language, which should automate the workflow in the respective software.

4. Developing a software which is ready to use, which can generate the surgical guide according to the surgeon's requirements from DICOM data.

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